
Medicinal Plants Resources Of Ghatanji Region, Dist. Yavatmal: A Documented Study

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Abstract:

Present paper deals with some ethno medicinal uses of 23 plant species, by the tribal of Ghatanji region, in Yavatmal district of Maharashtra. A number of villages were visited in this region. The information was documented involving field study by contacting and interviewing traditional healers for plants used in cure of various diseases. This region is inhabited by tribal communities like Banjara, Gond, Mang, Paradhi etc. The ethno botanical information on plants viz., botanical name, family, local name, plant part used and mode of administration is enumerated. The present information is used in drug standardization and estimation of compound content for further studies.

Keywords: Traditional Healers, Tribal People, Medicinal Plant, Ghatanji region, Yavatmal district.

Introduction:

India is sitting on a gold mine of well-recorded and traditionally well-practiced knowledge of herbal medicine. This country is perhaps the largest producer of medicinal herbs and called "Botanical garden of the world". India officially recognizes over 3000 plants for their medicinal value. It is estimated that over 6000 plants in India are in traditional use. The herbal medicine representing about 75% medicinal needs of the third world countries. There are about 7000 firms manufacturing traditional medicines with or without standardization (Choudhary, et al. 1998).

In India, it is reported that traditional healers use 2500 plant species and 100 species of plants serve as regular sources of medicine, Pei (2001). Plants are the basis of life on earth and are central to people's livelihoods. Tribal people are the ecosystem people who live in harmony with the nature and maintain a close link between man and environment. Indian subcontinent is

being inhabited by over 53.8 million tribal people in 5000 forest dominated villages of tribal community and comprising 15% of the total geographical area of Indian landmasses, representing one of the greatest emporia of ethno-botanical wealth (Chowdhari S. K., 2000). Therefore, effort should be initiated for the documentation and computerization of useful medicinal plants and their traditional knowledge (Mehrotra & Mehrotra, 2005).

The value of medicinal plants to the mankind is very well proven. It is estimated that 70 to 80% of the world population rely chiefly on traditional health care system and largely on herbal medicines (Shanley and Luz, 2003). Only 15% of pharmaceutical drugs are consumed in developing countries (Toledo, 1995). The affluent people have little alternative to herbal medicine, and they depend on traditional health care system (Marshall, 1998).

Yatoo Ghulam et. al., 2015, documented 48 plant species medicinally

used on various different ailments from Amravati district. Thirty plant species from Jalgaon District are useful for different human ailments (Pawar S. and D. A. Patil, 2004). The documented 39 plant species used in treatment of reproductive disorders while 20 monocotyledonous plant species are used in various diseases by the tribal of Umarched tehsil in Yavatmal district. They have further documented 36 ethnic formulations that are prepared using 50 plant species by locals of Umarched tehsil (Bhogaonkar and Kadam, 2005 and 2006). The 177 medicinal plants are used by Banjaras of Vidarbha on various ailments (Bhogaonkar and Chavhan, 2013).

In the present paper, folk medicinal preparations of 23 plant species used for different ailments has been enumerated.

Study Area:

The district Yavatmal is situated in the eastern part of the Maharashtra between north latitudes $19^{\circ} 23'$ and $20^{\circ} 48'$ and longitudes $77^{\circ} 19'$ and $79^{\circ} 07'$. It occupies an area of 13,582 Sq. Km.

The Ghatanji region is situated in eastern part of the Maharashtra between north latitudes 20.1437° N and longitudes 78.3117° E respectively. It occupies an area of 954.46 sq. meters. According to the census of 2011, the total population of the region was 138,587.

Material and Methods:

Tribal medicine practitioner men, village heads and local people were interviewed to record different plant part used for folk remedies. Plants were collected, documented and identified with the help of standard floras (Hooker 1997, Cooke 1967, Naik 1998, Yadav and

Sardesai, 2002) and herbarium specimens were prepared.

Enumeration:

The interviewed of local people and tribal medicine men's information are recorded, is as follows-

Sr. No.	Plant Name	Family	Local Name	Part Used	Mode of Uses
1.	<i>Abrus precatorious</i> L.	Fabaceae	Gunj	Root	Throat infection
2.	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Asteraceae	Osadi	Leaves	Skin diseases
3.	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Simaroubaceae	Maharukh	Leaves, Bark	Stomachic
4.	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall. ex Bedd.	Combretaceae	Dhawada	Gum	Tonic
5.	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Caesalpiniaceae	Aapta	Bark	Diabetes
6.	<i>Buchanania cochinchinensis</i> (Lour.) Almeida	Anacardiaceae	Charoli, Char	Leaves	Dysentery
7.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Caesalpiniaceae	Bahava, Amaltas	Seed	Dysentery
8.	<i>Cayratia trifolia</i> (L.) Domin.	Vitaceae	Ambatvel	Root	Tympany
9.	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Kurdu	Root	Sunstroke, Strong teeth
10.	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i> DC.	Meliaceae	Bhirra, Behera	Outer & Inner Bark	Wounds, Jaundice
11.	<i>Curculigo orchiodes</i> Gaertn.	Hypoxidaceae	Kali musali	Rhizome	Piles
12.	<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i> (Wall. Ex DC.) Seem	Bignoniaceae	Medhshingi	Leaves, Outer Bark	Tetanus, Wounds and Cutting
13.	<i>Enicostemma axillare</i> (Lam.) Raynal	Gentianaceae	Nai, Naichapala	Whole Plant	Fever, Diabetic
14.	<i>Euphorbia microphylla</i> Heyne	Euphorbiaceae	Dudhi	Leaves	Headache
15.	<i>Euphorbia parviflora</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Dudhi	Milky Latex	Headache
16.	<i>Ficus amplissima</i> J. E. Sm.	Moraceae	Pimpari	Bark	Typhoid
17.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Pimpal	Leaves	Eczema
18.	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr	Flacourtiaceae	Kakai	Leaves	Jaundice
19.	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) Schult.	Periplocaceae	Kawalvel, Anantmul	Root, Stem	Diuretic
20.	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker-Gawl.	Convolvulaceae	Pingalichave 1	Root	Dogbit
21.	<i>Maytenus emarginata</i> (Willd.) Ding Hou	Celastraceae	Bharati	Root	Leucorrhoea
22.	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Erandi	Leaves	Jaundice
23.	<i>Ventilago denticulata</i> Willd.	Rhamnaceae	Sakal vel	Bark	Dysentery.

Results and Discussion:

The present communication deals with the local people of Ghatanji region, Yavatmal District (M. S.), India were used

medicinally important plants of 19 genera and 23 species of angiosperms for different ailments. These are herb, shrub, climber, small and large trees. Among tribal communities, leaves (29%), roots (22%) and

bark (15%) are the most widely used plant parts, with gum, milky latex and stems also playing a significant role. These plants are common and medicinally important to treat various diseases like Jaundice, fever, tympany, tetanus, dysentery, eczema, dog

bit, leucorrhoea etc. Some therapeutic uses of such plants in Ghatanji region were documented. The present information is used in drug standardization and estimation of compound content for further studies.

Conclusion:

Traditional knowledge systems cure different diseases by the tribal of Ghatanji region. They use plant as a source of drug through trial and error basis and the process is experienced over hundreds of years. It has been observed that the use of the medicinal plants is also a routine practice in the local people.

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